

**THE MOST IMPORTANT ELEMENTS OF CLT TECHNOLOGY IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE IN FUTURE
FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS.**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7634166>

Abstract. This article is devoted to the model of communication culture formation of future foreign language teachers. In recent years, in our country, CLT (Communicative language teaching) teaching technology has become more and more popular in the development of communication culture of future personnel in English. In this technology, language is used as a means of communication, and it is related to all the surrounding circumstances in which it is happening - event, participants, goals, location, etc. Therefore, it is necessary for future foreign language teachers to organize communication provided with contextual elements that influence the ways of expressing and perceiving language-messages in the development of communication culture.

Key words: communicative culture, grammatical rules, educational activities, linguistic competence, socio-cultural competence, strategic competence, practical competence, speech competence

Today, the need to communicate in English is increasing day by day. This means that future foreign language teachers studying in higher education institutions need to be educated at the level of native speakers. Thus, it is extremely important for students to develop all types of speech activity equally in teaching English, and it represents the need to organize educational activities based on innovative methods and introduce effective interactive methods into the educational process.

In recent years, in our country, CLT (Communicative language teaching) teaching technology has become more and more popular in the development of communication culture of future personnel in English. In this technology, language is used as a means of communication, and it is related to all the surrounding circumstances in which it is happening - event, participants, goals, location, etc. Therefore, it is necessary for future foreign language teachers to organize communication provided with contextual elements that influence the ways of expressing and perceiving language-messages in the development of communication culture. "Language use" refers to the essential teaching or use of language in communicative language teaching. This differs from grammar-based

approaches. It becomes a communication skill that embodies all the possibilities of situations and goals that we can encounter in real life, that is, in everyday life, in workplaces, in the transition from monologue to dialogue, in interpersonal communication, and in other situations.

One of the most important learning theories of CLT is that "people learn language better when they use it to do something, rather than by learning how it works and applying the rules." This refers to the attitude towards previous learning practices aimed at learning grammatical rules, but students fail in oral communication. In addition, the teacher should not over-influence the students to learn grammar, because it is desirable for students to communicate in English, not grammar [1,114].

The comprehensive theory of learning CLT technology in the development of students' communication culture in English is described as follows:

- a. Various activities help to learn real communication.
- b. Activities in the language used to complete meaningful tasks help learning.
- c. Language that is meaningful to students supports the learning process [2;2].

So, it is worth mentioning that in higher education, we should focus on the meaningful and useful use of students' educational activities in English. This is because they can involve authentic communication and enable students to use the language for meaningful tasks in the classroom.

CLT plays an important role in the development of communication culture . The main features of CLT can be explained as follows:

- a. Emphasis on learning to interact in the target language through dialogue.
- b. Incorporating real texts into learning activities.
- c. Providing opportunities to attract students' attention not only to the language, but also to the learning process itself.
- d. Enhancing students' personal experiences as important contributors to classroom learning.
- e. An attempt to link language learning in the classroom with language activation outside the classroom [3;279].

The main assumptions or options in CLT practice are highlighted as follows:

- a. Learning a second language becomes easier when students interact and have meaningful communication.
- b. Tasks and exercises in the study sessions give students the opportunity to discuss the meaning of words in the language being studied, expand their language resources, experience how the language is used and understand the content.

- c. Students' communication is reflected in their processing of content that is meaningful, purposeful, interesting, and engaging.
- d. Communication is an integrated process that often requires the use of several language skills or techniques.
- e. Facilitates language learning through organizing activities that include a variety of inductive or exploratory learning in language learning, as well as activities that involve language analysis and reflection
- f. Language learning is a gradual process involving creative use of language and trial and error. While mistakes are a normal product of learning, the main goal of learning is to use a new language both correctly and fluently.
- g. Students develop their own orientations to language learning, progress through different paces, and have different needs and motivations for language learning.
- h. It involves successful and effective language learning through the use of communication strategies .

The role of educators in language teaching is to create an audience environment conducive to language learning and provide opportunities for prospective staff to use and practice language and reflect on language learning.

j. An audience is a learning community for students through collaboration and sharing [4;23].

Therefore, in the development of the components of the above communicative competence, the language is considered as a means of educational material. Special attention should be paid to all elements in the events held in the auditorium. Aspects of the given materials should include the factors that give meaning to the language at the time of occurrence (context), and should be provided with the skills necessary to express and understand the language used (communicative competence). Therefore, the goal of language teaching shifts from the acquisition of grammar to the development of communicative competence in part of the students. In general, the goal of CLT is to develop students' communicative competence.

As mentioned above, the goal of CLT is to develop communicative competence in the development of communicative culture in students. There are several theories about this, but the most important elements of communication competence are:

Figure 1. The most important elements of CLT technology in the development of communicative culture in future foreign language teachers

1. Linguistic competence . Grammar, vocabulary, morphology, i.e. grammatical competence related to the mastery of language elements is also recognized.
2. Socio-cultural competence . It is also known as sociolinguistic competence and social value system, which requires the correct use of language.
- 3 . Strategic competence . It has to do with effective communication and the strategies used to keep the communication going.
4. Current competence . It is related to the physical state of communication when speaking, for example: pronunciation.
- 5 . Speech competence . It represents the correct use of the elements of language formation and purposeful communication in different genres, coherence (structural connection) and coherence (meaningful relations in language). It is also known as pragmatic competence.

In fact, five components of communicative competence are expressed as a means of developing the teaching material of each language. All of the above elements are materials intended to attract the events held in the auditorium.

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